

PATIENT RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT: A CRM APPROACH TO PANDIAN MULTISPECIALITY HOSPITAL, MADURAI

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Abstract:

In the business world, customer relationship management is used to retain customer loyalty in order to increase revenue. Healthcare organizations can build the same kind of relationship with patients, and it can also offer more tangible benefits. The first benefit is by using the same hospital a patient’s treatment history should be relatively well known by the organization. Oftentimes, different hospitals use different patient information systems which are not always compatible with each other. If a patient keeps changing the hospital, his or her medical record can be scattered around various sites. Ideally, if the patient is treated by the same physician in every visit, that physician will get more familiar with the patient, which could improve treatment. The most tangible benefit, however, is time. If the patient goes to the same physician every time, there is no need for long check-ups at the beginning of each visit.

Key Words: CRM; Patient Communication; Patient Satisfaction; Compliance; Counseling

About SPS Chilling Center:

Pandian Multispeciality Hospital (S. R. Trust), in pursuit of medical excellence, has been delivering world-class treatment and care, at an affordable cost. With over 700 beds, Pandian Multispeciality Hospital has grown to be a multi-specialty hospital, touching lives in and around Madurai. We extend the traditional Indian hospitality to international patients, combining it with our cutting edge technology, clinical excellence and compassion to deliver quality health care to all patients every single day. We have shouldered social responsibility and have pioneered several charity initiatives. We have fostered an environment in which every person is motivated to continually improve the efficiency and effectiveness in the management of health care services. S.R. Trust is a non-profit organization registered under the Indian Trust Act (May 9, 1985). It was Mr. Lal Beer, an American Christian Missionary, who taught Dr. S. Pandian the valuable lessons of ethics, ideals and values to develop into a moral person in life. This beacon of light guides Pandian Multispeciality Hospital even today.

Introduction:

A PRM application also can provide better care for patients by allowing hospitals a better understanding of patients’ needs and want through improved communication via follow-up systems. Understanding how the treatment has worked is crucial for physicians. By letting the physicians know, how satisfied the patients are, physicians can have a better understanding on how the treatments and operations they perform are working. Thus, having better patient relationships and better patient loyalty benefits both the

healthcare organization and the patient. Today, patients can easily find instructions for their treatment from the Web. When hospitals provide real time information and disseminate it to their current and potential patients it will help them to stay in touch with people as well as compete with other healthcare organizations for customers. Hospital management strategies should consider comprehensive, efficient hospital information systems which support a shift of focus to patients. With the idea of PRM, hospitals may be able to move on towards more customer-centric operations than before.

Statement of the Problem:

A technology enabled CRM strategy to the meet customer focused objectives involves the vast majority of any organization's activity. No doubt about that Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has become a top priority for companies seeking to gain competitive advantage in today's stormy economy. However, confusion reigns about exactly what CRM is, how to best implement it, or even what role it should play in enhancing customer interaction. Against this background, it will be worth, undertaking a study to evaluate the customer retention of selected hospital.

Objectives of the Study:

The development of Customer Relationship Management has been very essential to many business organizations, in ensuring good customer relations at all cost. In this regard, this dissertation generally aims on identifying the impact of CRM on organizational performance of "Pandian Multispecialty Hospital".

In particular, this study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To study about CRM in Pandian Multispecialty Hospital - some theoretical aspects.
- To examine the socio-economic factors impacts on the various schemes in Pandian Multispecialty Hospital.
- To offer suitable suggestion based on the analysis to improve the services in the hospital.

Needs of the Study:

Customer relationship management (CRM) helps businesses to gain an insight into the behavior of their customers and modify their business operations to ensure that customers are served in the best possible way.

Scope of the Study:

The study is of great importance to Management/Healthcare administrators to help them provide a better patient relationship management to satisfy the Patient's needs and wants for a sustainable "Customer" loyalty. Effective Healthcare is important to individuals and nations alike. Indeed, it is a basic ingredient in the formula for a stable productive society. Today however, there is growing concern over a looming crisis in healthcare. According to Wanless D (2010), the challenges are so complex, that healthcare systems around the world need to fundamentally change the way they do business without such change, projections suggest, the current system will eventually collapse.

Hypothesis of the Study:

It means tentative generalization of the validity of which remains the tested. In short it deals with certain assumptions made in the study.

Null Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by H_0

Alternative Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H_1

Research Design:

"A Research Design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with the economy in procedure". The research design adopted for the studies is descriptive design. The researcher has to describe the present situation in order to know the behavior of the consumers. Hence descriptive research study is used. Descriptive research can only report what has happened and what is happening.

Research Methodology:

The validity of any research is based on the systematic method of data collection and analysis. Both primary and secondary data were used for the present study. The primary data has been collected from sample respondents in Pandian Multispecialty Hospital, MADURAI for this purpose satisfied random sampling method was used to select the samples the researcher has approached the management of the Pandian multispecialty Hospital, Madurai city to collect the list of customers in the hospital. The interviews were collected from 100 respondents from this hospital. The present study highlights the extent of utilization of the hospital services by the selected sample respondents. It is also shed light on the common problems faced by the respondents. The major features of the service sector especially on hospital performance are protected in order to utilize the services as per the expectation of the patient (customer).

For this study data have been collected from both primary and secondary source. An exclusive field study and interview have been conducted secondary data have also been collected for the study from books, leading journals, newspapers, magazines and textbooks related to study and from the internet source. The collected data were analyzed through percentage, average, range, standard deviation and weighted average. In Connection with this two way tables were prepared and chi-square test were also employed to find the association ship, Like's scaling technique is used to identify the customer preference and satisfaction on the hospital services. Henry Garrets ranking method is also used to judge the ranking especially on the hospital services.

Method of Data Collections:

Data collection is a term used to describe process of preparing and collecting data. Systematic gathering of data for a particular purpose from various sources, that has been systematically observed, recorded, organized. Data are the basic inputs to any decision making process in business. In this survey in order to meet the objectives of the study both primary data and secondary data were collected.

Primary Data:

- Data Collection

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is the data that have been already collected by and readily available from other sources. Such data are cheaper and quickly obtained than the primary data. The secondary data are collected from the company records and magazines, journals, internet etc.,

Interviews:

An Interview of the staff has been conducted working in Pandian multispecialty Hospital schemes .The main purpose of this is to get information regarding various package available. Interview of customers is also conducted to assess their needs and expectations.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi-square Analysis
- Correlation

Review of Literature:

According to (Greenberg 2022) "CRM isn't a technology, as you will see, that is true, but not strictly. We also heard that it was a customer facing system. That is a strategy and / or a set of business process, a methodology. It is all of the above or whichever you choose"

According to Croteau and Li, (2022) while retaining customer loyalty has been a sale principle for a very long time, according to). CRM is actually a tremendous step forward in creating a system that can provide a means for retaining individual loyalty in a world of many souls. In order to Understand CRM, one must also understand the changing nature of the Customer because Customer are not what they used to be

According to Brown (2022), CRM Is neither a concept nor a project, Instead a business strategy, which aims to understand, anticipated and manages the needs of the organizational current and potential customer. It is a journey of strategic, process, organizational and technical change where by, a company seeks to better manage it is own enterprise around customer behaviors. CRM is the process of acquiring, retaining and growing profitable customers. It requires a clear focus on the service attributes that represent value of the customer and create loyalty.

CRM is the point of view of Harris (Harris 2022) is a technology - enabled steategy to convert data driven into business actions in response to, and in anticipation of actual customer behaviors, from a technology perspective CRM represents a process to measure and allocate organizational resources to activity that has the greatest returns and impact on profitable customer relationship.

CRM is also considered by (Nilcollect, Andeen and Gilbert, 2021) as an enterprise – wide business strategy design to optimize profitability revenue and customer satisfaction by organization the enterprise around customer segment, fostering customer satisfying behavioral and linking process from customers through supplies

Conclusion and Recommendations:

The results of this study have clearly shown that successful implementationof Customer Relationship Management will bring about improve servicequality in health organizations. It was also revealed that Personalisation, Interactive Management and Relations with Patient are importantcomponents of Customer Relationship Management. Based on the aboveresults the following recommendations are made:

- There are health organizations with wide size and scope, in such a situation pre-planning is very essential for a successful implementation of CRM.
- A successful implementation of CRM requires an understanding of the expectations and needs of stockholders involved. This underscores the importance of patient feedback as one of the mechanisms of bringing about improves quality health services to the people.

- There is need to address the human aspect of the Implementation. The health workers Most especially, Doctors and Nurses, supposed to be trained thoroughly about Customer Relationship Management and how it can be successfully implemented in organization.
- There is need for executive support, so as to provide high level top management representation for the CRM project.

However, there are several limitations to this study amongst which include: The belief that the use of CRM could bring about Patient loyalty. However, there are other things that can bring about patient loyalty like billing method, location, and peer recommendation. The statement obtained from some respondents clearly indicated that some at the top management level didn't have knowledge of CRM and their responses were based on subjective perceptions and not objective data.

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